

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF NEW QUALITIES IN THE MENTAL DEVELOPMENT OF ADOLESCENTS

Aribjanova Umidakhon Aribjanova

Doctoral student of the Department of General Psychology,
Andizhan State University Andizhan Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5942919>

Annotation: The purpose of writing this article. Creating a healthy family psychological environment in the formation of positive qualities in adolescents. and understanding the direct impact of social factors and finding psychological ways.

Keywords: differential character, future profession, behavioral ethics, voluntary business.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ НОВЫХ КАЧЕСТВ В ПСИХИЧЕСКОМ РАЗВИТИИ ПОДРОСТКОВ.

Аннотация: Цель написания данной статьи. Создание здоровой семейной психологической среды в формировании положительных качеств у подростков. понимание прямого воздействия социальных факторов и поиск психологических путей

Ключевые слова: дифференциальный характер, будущая профессия, этика поведения, добровольный бизнес.

Uzbekistan is a country of young people. Therefore, special attention is paid to the education and development of young people. First of all, the legal framework for the organization of work in this area is constantly being improved. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Fundamentals of State Youth Policy" covers the issues of legal and social protection of young people, the support of their talents. The law regulates the powers of the authorities and other social relations in this area. The initiatives of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in improving the youth policy in the new Uzbekistan in line with modern requirements should be especially noted. The constant attention of the head of our state to the development of young people is especially evident in the education reforms. The success of these reforms is strengthening young people's confidence in the state and the law.

In particular, one of our Jadids, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, thinking about the development and prospects of the nation, the future of Turkestan, came to the conclusion that the only way to save the people from the swamp of ignorance, freedom and poverty is to be enlightened. was. Behbudi, on the other hand, sent

Turkestan's young people, who were interested in collecting money from the people and studying science, but whose parents could not afford it, to foreign engineers to teach engineers and teachers necessary for the development and future of the nation. He put forward the idea of boosting the country's development by having modern scientists who trade in European markets and know the foreign language. Abdurauf Fitrat, one of the Jadids It is impossible to reform a society without educating it, to direct its development to development. He argues that the fate of a nation depends on the condition of its family: "The happiness and dignity of any nation depends, of course, on the discipline of the families of that nation. Where family relationships are based on strong discipline, so is the country and the nation. " The initiatives and ideas put forward at the meeting of the head of our state with the youth are proof of this. Where family relationships are based on strong discipline, the country and the nation will be just as strong. " The initiatives and ideas put forward at the meeting of the head of our state with the youth are proof of this. Where family relationships are based on strong discipline, so is the country and the nation. " The initiatives and ideas put forward at the meeting of the head of our state with the youth are proof of this. Even today, in the days of quarantine, the issue of educating the future youth of our country as a fully developed, educated, talented person is approached in a unique and modern way, the organizational and legal framework for protecting all their rights, freedoms, opportunities and interests is growing. After all, the fact that distance education is organized in a continuous online manner and ensures the right of young people to education is a practical expression of the care and attention that Uzbekistan provides to young people today. After all, our country is a country of happy youth, and about 64% of the population of our country are young people, ie under 30 years old. Of course, given the great responsibility of our state, it requires a lot of attention and care, and on the other hand, the attention paid to our youth will bring great success and results tomorrow. Because now more than half of Uzbekistan's labor force is young. In the future, every third leader will be young.

For this reason, young people have always been recognized as an active layer of society. During the Eastern Renaissance, as well as in the activities of the Jadids, the role of youth in the renewal of society was invaluable. In this regard, this layer, which is constantly evolving, requires constant guidance and support. system represents public policy on youth.

A healthy family psychological environment leads in the formation of positive qualities in adolescents. By studying the psychological characteristics inherent in adolescence, it is possible to understand the ways in which the personality of adolescents is formed, developed, and matured, and the direct influence of biological and social factors that affect it. Sexual maturation influences adolescent behavior at this age as a primary biological agent. But this is a direct effect. The psychological "mechanism" of adolescence is schematically assessed as follows. The onset of puberty, which is associated with the appearance of endocrine hormones and their effects on the central nervous system, increases the physical and psychological potential of children's activity and makes them feel like adults, leads to a favorable environment for them to feel feelings of independence. However, even at this stage of mental development, the child is not yet fully ready to act independently. The social factors are: the transition from primary to secondary school, ie from the leadership of a single teacher to the majority of teachers, and changes in communication, the expansion of socially useful work, the development of independent and practical work. Implementation is also a change in the child's place in the family. Compared to older adolescents, the incompatibility that occurs in younger adolescents is not due to their sexual maturity, but to the circumstances around them, the attitude of the parents in the family, the attitude of the siblings to it, the neighborhood, that is, social conditions. 'must be associated with the secret. It is these social conditions that directly affect the behavior of adolescents by changing their psychological climate, misbehavior, stubbornness, non-recognition of their shortcomings. can prevent negative traits such as. During this period, the teenager says goodbye to a happy childhood, but is in a state where he has not yet found his place in adult life. The teenager tries to solve complex life problems without properly assessing his abilities and strengths, but because his thinking ability is superficial, he makes a number of shortcomings in his daily life. But he prefers to argue with adults rather than admitting his mistake. He doesn't like people who criticize him, every criticism seems to be a sign of ignoring him, a deliberate act. He is independent, tries to act arbitrarily, ignoring the advice of adults. Some teens begin to learn a variety of negative habits to demonstrate that they have joined the ranks of adults. Such changes in adolescent behavior are of great concern to teachers and parents. In order to change them for the better, it requires psychological knowledge and experience from adults. At this age, helping adults in a psychological way, rather than embarrassing, discriminating, or criticizing the shortcomings and mistakes that adults unknowingly leave behind, puts an end to the feeling of "adulthood."

rather, it should mean how an adult should be and what requirements he or she should meet. Some teens begin to learn a variety of negative habits to demonstrate that they have joined the ranks of adults. Such changes in adolescent behavior are of great concern to teachers and parents. In order to change them for the better, it requires psychological knowledge and experience from adults. At this age, helping adults in a psychological way, rather than embarrassing, discriminating, or criticizing the shortcomings and mistakes that adults unknowingly leave behind, puts an end to the feeling of "adulthood." rather, it should mean how an adult should be and what requirements he or she should meet. Some teens begin to learn a variety of negative habits to demonstrate that they have joined the ranks of adults. Such changes in adolescent behavior are of great concern to teachers and parents. In order to change them for the better, it requires psychological knowledge and experience from adults. At this age, helping adults in a psychological way, rather than embarrassing, discriminating, or criticizing the shortcomings and mistakes that adults unknowingly leave behind, puts an end to the feeling of "adulthood." rather, it should mean how an adult should be and what requirements he or she should meet. In order to change them for the better, it requires psychological knowledge and experience from adults. At this age, helping adults in a psychological way, rather than embarrassing, discriminating, or criticizing the shortcomings and mistakes that adults unknowingly leave behind, puts an end to the feeling of "adulthood." rather, it should mean how an adult should be and what requirements he or she should meet. The adolescent's claim to new rights will primarily apply to the entire environment of interactions with adults. The adolescent now begins to resist the demands he or she used to have: he or she becomes very upset when his or her independence is limited, guardianship, guidance, control, obedience, punishment, and disregard for his or her interests, attitudes, and opinions. protests. The adolescent develops a sense of self-worth and sees himself as a person who cannot be discriminated against, deprived of the right to independence. Parents and educators need to work with adolescents individually to please them and to correct their behavior in a timely manner. Some teachers believe that these changes in a young teenager - negative symptoms,

aggression, they make misdiagnosis and conclusions without knowing where the roots of their stubbornness come from and what it is connected with, and what the consequences are, which can often lead to tragedy. One of the main conflicting factors is that the adolescent overestimates his or her independence. There is a discrepancy between the overestimation of one's own abilities and the mental abilities of the young adolescent. Disobedience to the will of adults, disobedience to the decisions of school, class activists, etc. - this is not only the only reaction to the inability to adequately assess the situation, but also a way for the teenager to introduce himself to others from his personal point of view. also serves as. In this way, the child learns the importance of his personality, Adolescents still can't be considered fully grown. Because their personal characteristics can still be traced back to childhood. This is reflected in the assessments they make in their minds, in their attitudes towards life and their future. Many teens are irresponsible about choosing a career when they graduate. This period is characterized by the adolescent's moral self-awareness, as well as the transition to a new stage of morality. Well-developed adolescents are able to understand and discuss issues of concern to adults. teenagers think the answers to many problematic questions. Their attention is drawn to more ethical issues. If the source of ethical issues for primary school students is teachers for them, adolescents seek answers to these questions more in the circle of their peers. Adolescents, on the other hand, turn to resources that more adults use to find the right answer to a question. Such sources are mainly real, multifaceted, complex human relations and scientific-popular fiction, non-fiction, industrial works, press, radio, television. Today's teenagers have a vigilant, mental and practical outlook on life, freedom and independence. They also have a realistic approach to the concept of being honest. For example, as in previous years, they understand and interpret that "justice is not the same for everyone, but is determined by everyone according to his ability and his contribution to everyone's work or human interests." By the time they finish school, many teenagers will have morally shaped and hardened certain moral norms. In addition to the moral worldview, adolescents develop certain views on social, political, economic, scientific, cultural, religious, and other areas. For many years, teenagers have been concerned about good and evil, truth and lawlessness, morality and immorality. Adolescents of today are not confident or negative about everything, but young people who look at life realistically, mentally, practically, and strive to be more free and independent. Adolescents strive to regulate their behavior based on consciously acquired moral norms. This is manifested primarily in the growth of the adolescent's self-awareness. Self-awareness is a

complex psychological structure that includes: First, a child's sensations arising from the influence of an object in the external world begin to differentiate with his own body. The second is his understanding of his personal "I" based on his active activities. Third is his understanding of his own mental characteristics and traits. Fourth is an understanding of a particular system of social, moral self-assessment. It is possible that all of these elements are functionally and genetically linked to each other. But all of this, you know, doesn't happen all at once. A child's understanding of 'I' appears around the age of 3, when the child begins to use a personal pronoun. For example: I, mine, me and so on to understand their mental qualities and self-esteem in adolescence, is becoming more and more important. Adolescents begin to observe their personal characteristics as soon as they have the ability to express themselves everywhere. That is, they begin to look critically at their appearance: low neck or, conversely, obesity, facial expressions annoy young men and women, they suffer. Late-aged boys and girls have secret experiences. A person's self-image is a very important component of self-awareness. During adolescence, self-esteem increases. the teenager becomes increasingly self-aware of his worth, what he deserves to do, and what he is capable of. Self-assessment comes in 2 ways. One evaluates the results of one's achievements. For example: The child does not lose himself in a difficult situation or rescued a young child from a fire - he says, "I'm not a coward." He did a certainly difficult task. "I'm talented," he says. Such moral behavior is a test of a teenager's self-discipline During adolescence, mainly cognitive processes develop at a high level. During these years, the basic personal and entrepreneurial traits that teens will need throughout their lives will begin to become apparent. Memory rises from the level of mechanical memory to the level of logical memory. Speech is advanced, diverse and rich thinking develops in all its manifestations: dynamic, figurative, logical. Adolescents can now be taught a variety of practical and mental activities. It is also during this period that general and special abilities are formed and developed. Adolescence is characterized by many contradictions and contradictions. The intellectual development of adolescents, who stand out in mastering the school curriculum and solving various problems related to other activities, encourages adults to think with them about serious problems, the teenagers themselves try to do the same. On the other hand, infantilism (physical and psychological condition specific to young children) can be observed, especially in the discussion of issues such as future profession, behavioral ethics, responsibility for their obligations. Students in grades 5-6 are more likely to pay close attention to their position in the classroom. Especially from 6th grade

onwards, students begin to pay attention to their appearance, as well as children of the opposite sex and their interactions with them. 7th graders have a unique interest in developing their abilities. Grade 8 students, on the other hand, value personal qualities that are associated with independence, originality, friendship, and camaraderie. Adolescents can actively develop willpower entrepreneurship and other useful qualities based on the interests that emerge in this series. During adolescence, with the teaching of academic subjects by different teachers, new criteria for assessing the personality and activities of adults also begin to take shape. Adolescents are generally knowledgeable, demanding, honest, able to deliver learning material in an interesting and understandable way, do not discriminate against students, and have more respect and love for teachers. They also place great emphasis on their relationship with the teacher. There are also changes in the motivations of children aged 10-15 years. During early adolescence, most adolescents give themselves a negative personal characteristic. As a teenager, self-esteem begins to manifest itself in a differential nature (behavior, behavior in social situations, and certain behaviors). Every parent, every household, every neighborhood, today considers the education of our children as the most important task, able to protect young people from negative influences that are alien to our people and harmful to the consciousness of the new generation, to show the world and national development to the world community. the upbringing of the younger generation is both a duty and an obligation. After all, human life is directly related to morality, education. Remember, the new youth of Uzbekistan is the foundation of our future and prospects. Today, it is both a duty and an obligation to protect the youth from the negative influences alien to our people and the consciousness of the new generation, to bring up a young generation capable of showing the development of the nation and the state to the world community. After all, human life is directly related to morality, education. Remember, the new youth of Uzbekistan is the foundation of our future and prospects. Today, it is both a duty and an obligation to protect the youth from the negative influences alien to our people and the consciousness of the new generation, to bring up a young generation capable of showing the development of the nation and the state to the world community. After all, human life is directly related to morality, education. Remember, the new youth of Uzbekistan is the foundation of our future and prospects.

References:

1. K. Sodikov SH Aripova G A Shakhmurova Young physiology and hygiene Tashkent «Yangi asr avlodi» 2009 103 p
2. G ' . B. Shoumarov Family Psychology Publishing and Printing Joint-Stock Company "SHARQ" Edited by TASHKENT - 2010 Page 97
3. L. Beknazarova, M. Maxmudova, B. Shodiev Socio-psychological training (Scientific-methodical manual) "Wing of thinking" Tashkent-2016
4. PI Ivanov ME Zufarova General Psychology «Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan» Tashkent-2008 page 63
5. ZT Nishonova NG` Komilova DU Abdullayeva Developmental psychology Tashkent 2019.
6. Davlatshen MG Age and pedagogical psychology. Tashkent 2009

